

Retailing to E-Tailing : Evolution to Revolution

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Abstract

Over the past decade consumers and companies have experienced a vibrant and revolutionary change in the way marketing and advertising have been applied to new and existing products and services. These changes are being promoted by advances in technology that have led to increasing growth of communication through interactive media, primarily the Internet. Today, most companies are delving into Internet marketing to reach, capture and keep consumers returning to increase brand loyalty and build relationships with their customers.

Internet retailing is developing rapidly, and research on Internet retailing management has important theoretical and practical significance. In the market, failed and successful websites coexists. What factors affect the failures and successes of running Internet retailing? How should a firm design their business model and evaluate it? Given the current state of e-commerce -and its potential-how should senior managers of physical retail stores be thinking about the priorities and directing their time, efforts, and resources? Has online shopping changed the way the top managers of “conventional” stores think about their products, services, and customers? Should it?

The aim of this paper is to review and take stock of challenges resulting from changes brought by internet which in consequences senior managers and researchers of retailing face as a new century begins.

Introduction

E-retailing selling of retail goods and services over the internet. This buzzing word which is influencing shopping pattern of today’s customers and bringing major revolution in retail marketing is not a stand-alone word but it’s a part of E-Commerce which has brought the gyration in physical Commerce industry.

“**Electronic commerce** is an emerging model of new selling and merchandising tools in which buyers are able to participate in all phases of a purchase decision, while stepping through those processes electronically rather than in a physical store or by phone (with a physical catalog). The processes in electronic commerce include enabling a customer to access product information, Right Now, opinions about the impact of the internet on conventional brick and mortar retailers, catalogs, and even door to door selling are extremely different.

One school of thought maintains that ecommerce will affect all retailers and all types of products, that the internet will change the face of retailing thoroughly and permanently.

Another school believes that the internet is not as much an issue for bricks and mortar retailers as it is for direct mail retailers, that it will prove easier for consumers to switch from one catalog shopping to online shopping, but that most people who are currently enjoy shopping face to face will not find the new medium particularly attractive.

The truth is that the internet's effect on retailing is many, many shades of gray. And that means that senior managers' responses should range accordingly. Some have already felt the impact of the internet. For others, the eye of storm is long way off. As the consumers become more familiar with the technology, and as they become increasingly aware that they can shop for items across ever greater distances-indeed, across borders-senior managers will have to take a hard, new look at their products and services, at their own potential for on-line sales, and at the threat of competition. Right now, not many appliances are sold over the internet especially the electronic products. **Any product that doesn't need to look at carefully or touch is a fair game in e-tailing.**

Retailing no longer involves just growth or expansion into new geographic, product, or customer segment markets. Companies are now learning to shift their emphasis to manage their business in this technology driven digital era.

There are six major incentives for firms to adopt Internet retailing viz. improving internal communication, improving operational efficiency, facing competition, enhancing customer services, reaching out to a wider audience, and improve relations with suppliers.

E-Retailing-a roadmap to change in retailing

Retailing is the set of business activities that adds value to the products and services sold to consumers for their personal or family use. Internet retailing is the retailing business on the Internet. That is to say, on one side, providers sell products or provide services on online website; on the other side, consumers buy products or services by accessing such website via connected computers (i.e., Internet). Digital products will be delivered to customers by Internet directly and non-digital products will be delivered by logistics. Also Known As: Internet Retail, Retail E-Commerce, Online Retailing, E-Retail, E-tail, E-tailing

Doherty and Ellis-Chadwick classified the studies of Internet retailing into three categories:

The first category is the studies from customer perspective, taking the focus on customer online purchasing behavior and psychology.

The second category is the studies from retailer (i.e., company) perspective, taking the focus on the retailing management, such as business model design and online store management.

The third category is those from technology perspective, taking the focus on the innovation of emerging IT for the online retailing management. For example, Flash can be used to enhance the display of products.

Hurdles in this path to change in retailing

Unlike brick mortar retailing, the computer retailing cannot convey the ambience. It can't tell you if your customers are particularly frustrated with pothole in the parking lot or particularly pleased with new way a store looks and smells. There is lack of understanding what and how customer is feeling. The internet has not changed priorities. It has simply added another layer of urgency to an already established agenda. Products and services are all on which businesses have to be built on. What on line shopping has done is forcing manager to examine their priorities in newly creative ways.

There are various factors that consumers weigh in determining whether they will patronize a particular store. The five main factors are as follows:

1. The breadth and depth of product assortment
2. The price of the goods sold,
3. Services
4. The convenience of the shopping experience(absence opening hours, travel time and parking)
5. Ambience

Right now the internet is more of the transactional-sales medium than a relationship building medium. Personal contact with highly trained and motivated salesperson-the service factor and in part the ambience factor-is still the critical differentiator for the premium branded goods and online experiences have yet to match that or offer a suitable counter value. But for the retailers that offer higher value branded convenience goods, the Internet is a more immediate concern.

However, some retailers fall back on the in-store experience as a point of differentiation both from retailers and ecommerce competitors as apart from the look of a store. It's very difficult to deliver a consistent in-store experience because there are all types of salesman and some are those who may not have any interest in product they are selling whereas it is routinely easy to offer a consistent experience on-line.

Building relationship with customer: With e-tailing the first question that comes to entrepreneur mind is can a technology provide ways to communicate with customers that add value to their relationships with them. On the one hand, it's not clear that customers would be ready to spend several thousand of dollars for a fine designer outfit they haven't touched or tried on. On the other hand, for the customers who are seeking many fashion basics, gifts, or tried and true products, the Internet may provide a more efficient shopping experience than a physical store. Challenge is to create a Web-based experience that exceeds customers' already high expectations.

Website with just a catalog or list of store events alone would not be particularly useful. Defining what will be useful is a hurdle.

Technology Hurdle: Technology affects which business is chosen to pursue through which channels. It will create new merchandising opportunities and challenges. The web enhances the ability to leverage sales associates' connection with their customers in systematic manner. The

challenge is to integrate the Internet with already formidable personalized communication and service capabilities. Executives should know that e-commerce means different things to different retailers. And they have pretty good idea about whether or how their particular businesses are currently suited to the web. But the advent and proliferation of online shopping should serve as a wake up call to any retailer that has not spent time seriously considering what brings its customer to its stores, catalogs, or websites, and what encourages them to spend money there. The priorities for the retailers remain the same: to meet and to exceed their customer expectation. So important thing for retailer is to try to understand whether, how, when, and how much their physical store should be linked to, or augmented by, on line shopping.

Customer servicing: The customer who comes to store to shop don't just want to shop for goods they need, they want everything that goes with those needs. They want to transform simple needs into a new style, a new feeling, or a new expression of themselves. The retail store of future must not only provide customers with goods but also offer them a whole new lifestyle.

In e-retailing, customers can find and order products that might not be available in the physical store most convenient to them. The gap order between physical store and mail order business can thus be effectively closed.

Retailers also worry that new technologies might threaten their existing business. Technology is just a platform for change. How this technology is being used to create value for customers is what will determine the future-that's the opportunity needed to be addressed.

Management Challenges in E-Retailing

As clear from hurdles in e-tailing section that it's not very easy to step into online retail business and get ensure profit, therefore in following section light is thrown on the key challenges that management should look into before setting up online business.

1. Know Yourself

Owning your own business can be a rewarding experience; the profits, the independence, and the lifestyle. From creating a vision for your business to the day to day operations, you have the ultimate authority in the decision making process. However, there are also many challenges that come with the operation of a business, whether it is a brick and mortar operation or a web-based E-Retail business. As an entrepreneur you must be able to deal with the rigors of hard work, day to day stress, and the risk of failure. Johnny Hart, author of the B.C. comic strip defines an entrepreneur as "a person who does everything he can think of to keep from getting a job."

Successful entrepreneurs typically have four main characteristics: need for achievement, willing to take risks, self-confidence, and a passion for the business. A self-evaluation will give a good indication if the initial requirements as an entrepreneur are met. Of course, there are always exceptions to every rule but these are very good indicators. In fact, the fourth characteristic, a passion for the business may be the most important. It indicates a willingness to make the commitment to hard work and the tenacity to succeed.

2. Know Your Customer

What an entrepreneur is planning to sell online and to whom is critical to the success of his E-Retail business.

A business plan will be the roadmap to success, but before a business plan is created entrepreneur may want to review the following lists for additional ideas on E-Retail business. The first list includes some of the typical E-Retail business ideas. The second list includes a number of things that can be done with their web site. Hopefully both will give clear ideas to create a winning online business.

What to sell online?

- Products that can sell cheaper
- Products that require consumer research
- Items that are hard to find (i.e., collectibles and specialty items)
- Products that appeal to tech-savvy users

What else can be done online?

- Increase brand or product awareness
- Enhancing corporate image
- Achieving market leadership
- Providing information and/or displaying samples of goods or services
- Building loyal relationships with customers
- Improving customer service
- Gathering information about customer needs and preferences to guide future product development
- Improving knowledge of customer demographics
- Testing consumer response to discounts or other special offers

3. Internationalism

In all advanced countries, retailing will be subject to increasing international influence. A partial list of reasons includes:

- Foreign companies (European, Middle Eastern, Western, Oriental, and others), all with large capital funds, are seeking investments in Indian, American retailing. Investment bankers and consulting organizations, acting for investors, are already seeking and frequently having success in making desired acquisitions.
- Some major U.S retailing companies are intensely interested in established foreign retailing divisions. In addition, other U.S retailers who already have foreign operations are interested in increasing their investments like Bharti-Walmart in India
- Some European and U.S. retailing organizations are interested in forming joint venture companies in India, Japan and transporting innovations form of merchandise to the Japanese, Indian economy.
- Consumers have become more cosmopolitan. The print media has become increasingly international in focus, motion pictures are now widely distributed internationally, and television entertainment programs and news broadcasts frequently have an international

origin. In addition, university-level students in growing numbers are pursuing education in foreign countries.

4. Life Style Marketing

The successful retailer of the 2000s may well be the one who is able to understand and cater to the unique lifestyle segments in his particular consumer market. Therefore stores unwilling to adopt product lines and services based on changing lifestyles not only will lose sales but will often be replaced by new institution. Ecommerce help in this consuming the product according to the customer life style.

Actually, this life style change is a result of the working woman's being a working wife or a working mother. Working woman view themselves as the most time pressed segments of the population. Working woman, therefore have less time, and views shopping as obligation rather than leisure time activity.

5. Self-Service Marketing

The concept of the super market is historically associated with grocery products. In reality, it is a certain method of operation-that is, stores with facilities to expedite customer self-service (generally providing a shopping cart), and designed to facilitate multiple item shopping using a central checkout for processing customer transactions and collecting merchandise data.

6. Consumerism

“Consumerism is fortified by a more sophisticated consuming public, many of whom are living under conditions of economic pessimism, with the generally held attitude that business is not operating in the consumer's best interest.”

From a strategic standpoint, consumerism provides an individual company with a wide range of choices, from minimum legal compliances with consumer oriented governmental restrictions to an offensive strategy which promotes the consumer's interest by providing better quality merchandise and better information.

We can expect that consumerism will continue in the 2Ks. Fueled by energy and inflation and more consumer education, the public will more and more often demand information or even be hostile.

Product safety and hazard information will also be of high interest to many consumers in the 2Ks.

7. Professionalism

Professionalism in management, while difficult to define precisely, is usually characterized by :

- A concern for “Return on Investment” concepts as opposed to the almost total preoccupation with management of profit margins as a percent of sales.
- MBO: “Management By Objectives,” a system which uses participative management with subordinates substantially influencing their own performance objectives and being judged on the basis of results rather than on effort expended; and
- MIS: A “Management Information System” which helps to operate the business by providing timely and relevant information.

Information, in essence the analysis and synthesis of data, will unquestionably be one of the most vital corporate resources in 2020s. It will be structured into models for planning and decision making, incorporated into measurements of performance and profitability and integrated into product design and marketing methods.

8. Productivity

As indicated earlier, the good old days of growth through expansion are just about gone, at least for the near term. Accordingly, consumer goods marketers will be looking for ways to improve the bottom line figure. Many organizations will strive to increase productivity. The major aspects of improvement have to do with people, assets, and facilities.

Since it is usually difficult to improve productivity by trying harder, the most important increases in productivity often come from doing things differently rather than doing things better such as the following changes could be made:

- **Shifting functions:** Have suppliers perform certain activities formerly handled by store personnel, such as price marking of goods, handling reorders, shelf stocking. In addition, shift to more self-service merchandising-get the consumer to do more of the job that used to be done by retail store employees.
- **Automation:** Consider mechanized warehousing and automatic order entry devices in communication with the supplier's computer. This replaces time spent between sales people and store buyers or order clerks.
- **Vertical merchandising:** Use vertical space more imaginatively by designing fixtures and store décor to accommodate merchandise assortments in a smaller amount of store space.

9. Market Share Management

Most of these strategic influences have to do with the adjustment of retailers and wholesalers of consumer goods to a lower growth rate than they experienced in the recent past. During the late 1990s and 2000s, new stores were opened to an incredible rate. This was encouraged by ever-increasing levels of income, and greatly facilitated by the institutional investor's extraordinary interest in new concept retailing companies.

Market Share management involves several very complex subjects. One of these being able to identify the stage in the life cycle that a store may be now in and the one it will be in the next few years.

At each stage of the life cycle, appropriate strategies must be chosen to cope with the problems of profitability at that stage and to insure that the right appeal is made to the customer market segments that are likely to be attracted to the company's products/ service offered at that stage.

A second problem is identifying the total market which is to be used for the purpose of monitoring market share performance. Historically, companies measured their performance against the actual or estimated performance of similar rivals.

10. Commitment

The commitment to the business is measured in time, energy and the skills that are brought by retailer with him to the business. Once business plan is created, there will be many hours of development time. Development time includes the planning of the E-Retail web site itself, the purchase of manufacturing of the products that are planned to sell, and the infrastructure required to operate the business.

Once the E-Retail business is operating, time is required to devote to update all of the above. The Internet is ever evolving so in order for web site to remain current it will be needed to update as the industry dictates. Retailer will also be constantly evaluating what customers are buying and not buying to adjust his product and product line.

Maintenance is another time commitment related to the technology of E-Retail business. As business grows e-retailer will be faced with decisions about how to handle the web site traffic. He will also have to make adjustments to the infrastructure of the business to handle increased shipping and customer service demands.

11. Costs

E-Retail business will incur startup costs similar to that of a brick and mortar business. The main difference is there will be no indication to anyone other than retailer and those working with him that anything is happening with their business.

The business plan created included a financial plan. It is difficult to predict costs because there are number of variables related to starting a new business.

12. Fraud

One of the concerns of E-Retailers is whether their customers believe they are a trustworthy seller. Developing a trusting relationship with a customer will take time and effort and it's no wonder. The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) reported that online scammers robbed Americans of more than \$437 million dollars in 2003 with Internet related fraud accounting for 55% of all fraud reports. According to report released by FTC in 2011, fraud related to internet constitutes 242035 complaints.

Strategies

With the invent of internet leading to vanishing of cross border, any Joe Merchant from anywhere can set up the online Web site to start a new venture. Customers now have more choices available with wide variety of product and number of online vendor available. So what will make retailer's site stand out in the E-commerce pool and shine depends on what type of strategies they follow to attract new customers and retain already existing customers.

Market positioning, business model, and estimation of market size are the key factors for a successful online retailing website. Business Model and marketing strategy should be designed according to three aspects of product, i.e. purchasing frequency, tangible or intangible, and differentiation.

A framework for evaluating the performance of retailing website consists of two facets of indicators, the user facet and the business facet. The user facet is made up with availability, customer loyalty, etc..And the business facet is made up with strategic positioning, technology, branding, complementarities, etc.

Various strategies that e-retailers must concentrate on are discussed below under three headings viz. technology point of view, branding point of view, customer point of view.

TECHNOLOGY POINT OF VIEW

1. Use technology to create immediate tangible benefit for the customer.

If consumers don't see how technology is going to help them, they often assume it's going to be used against them. When net banking was first introduced then people reacted negatively owing to revealing their confidential account information over the internet which can be eavesdropped.

In such a case where benefits of any technology are not visible and not immediately apparent, make it obvious through advertising and promotional materials.

2. Make technology easy to use.

Most internet technology is pretty complex. In Internet shopping, sites require consumers to navigate slightly differently, sites organize product categories in different ways, they provide different types of information about products and they have different procedures for ordering and fulfillment. It takes customers almost 20 to 30 minutes just to learn how to shop in most text based Internet based shopping systems. By contrast, it takes them only two to three minutes to learn how to shop in a 3D virtual store. So technology should be user friendly. It is very difficult to create one customer interface that works well for everyone.

3. Execution matters: prototype, test, and refine.

It is very difficult to create one customer interface that works well for everyone; therefore it is very important to recognize that customers' response to technology varies.

Many technologies are viable concepts but fail because of poor execution. So before implementation, first properly test the technology with properly designed samples and if found any flaw, make the appropriate improvements.

4. Build systems that are compatible with the way customers make decisions.

It's sad to say but many companies developing the next generation of customer interface technologies spend more time interacting with the computers rather than customers, As a result, the systems are often incompatible with customers' shopping habits

5. Study the effects of technology on what people buy, how they shop and coordinate all technologies that touch the customers.

Today's technologies can have equally profound effects on customers' behavior. For example, if any grocery store electronically adjusts prices according to the time of day, reducing prices in the evening, it may be able to increase evening sales by 40% and double store traffic.

In online shopping, brand names become less important as the amount of detailed information about a product's attributes increases.

When a customer encounters a retailer, it should not matter the encounter occurs via the internet, through catalog, by telephone, or in a physical store. The customer expects to find the same merchandise, offered at the same prices, with the same knowledgeable and courteous service. So, e-retailers should build a system that recognizes high rollers whether they are on-line, on the telephone.

6. Use technology to tailor marketing programs to individual customers' requirements.

Most conventional retailers design their stores, product offerings, promotions, and services for the masses. They treat all shoppers alike even though customers' needs and wants differ and so do the volume and profitability of their purchases. This is the area where e-retailers can act tactfully and adjust their marketing programs instantly to match the needs of individual shoppers. Retailers can tailor their services in any number of ways using the available technology, if they focus on how it can help them help their customers.

7. Build systems that leverage existing competitive advantage.

For many years, people have said that a store's location was a key for its success. Now the buzz is that, in the world of electronic retailing, location doesn't matter. A consumer can do a business with a merchant located across the country or border as easily as one located across the street. But some products can't be shipped at all. Customers may be reluctant to purchase of these products on-line because of lack of touch n feel factor there.

In such a case e-retailers can use technology to magnify rather than minimize the benefits of their physical store

STRATGIES BASED ON BRANDING

1. Branding Make Web Identity

Branding is the mirror of company which customers view to develop their attitude toward the companies. The competitive advantages of branding includes:

1. Reduces marketing costs.
2. More premium price over his competitive.
3. Launching extension under brand name.

2. Confidence + Trust=Successful Transactions

In online shopping the most important concern which customers have is not revealing their confidential information from the security point of view like credit card number and other details . Another issue that may arise is regarding whether customer will be able to get what exactly promised by online retailer. Building good brand name will help in winning the customer confidence so that he won't leave retailer website without completing transaction.

3. Old is Gold, New is Silver

Traditional Brick-Mortar retailers may use internet to wed their offline business with their online business. Internet may be used to promote their physical world outlet rather then

investing the total capital to set up online business in order to establish their brand name in internet world before coming as pure click and mortar retailer.

4. Commitment to Customers

Servicing is an area that determines the ultimate satisfaction of customers so retailers have the opportunity to use the internet as the tool to be more responsive to changing preference, requirement & need of customer.

5. Affinity for Something for Nothing

Customers may be given surprises based on purchasing and web site surfing pattern in the form of free gift hampers and discount vouchers which will help retailers to attract and retain more customers.

STRATEGIES BASED ON CUSTOMER POINT OF VIEW

Today, online merchants must cater to increasingly online-savvy, time-crunched consumers. The five top challenges E-tailer faces are:

- 1. Competitors are just a click away.** When consumers search, they have multiple options available, and many use search to navigate the Web rather than type in or bookmark specific sites.
- 2. Visitors can disappear in 15 seconds or less.** Online consumers are goal-oriented shoppers. If they don't immediately find what they're looking for when they reach your site or landing page, they're gone in under 15 seconds.
- 3. Shopping is a multistep process.** Online consumers love to browse. Many spend a fair bit of time visiting several sites just to gather information. They may also compare the offerings of several competitors before hitting the "buy now" button.
- 4. Time between initial visit and purchase has increased.** Increasingly financially challenged consumers may wait longer before buying.
- 5. Customers wait for merchants' best offer.** Having been seduced during the holiday season with free shipping and handling and other price-driven offers, consumers have been trained to wait for a special deal.

Pitfalls to avoid

When retailers run an online business he must be sure that his customers are satisfied in order to ensure business success. As retailer begins his online service there are several pitfalls he will need to avoid. If retailer don't have the drive, passion, or dedication he shouldn't start an online business since it takes these three elements in order for it to work.

- 1. Poor designing.** One thing retailer want to avoid is creating an ugly webpage. It should be attractive and easy to view things.

2. **Lack of correct information.** Retailers never want their information to be out of date. This information must be correct and filled with useful stuff. Pricing needs to be updated. Retailers don't want to lack any important information either. If there is a question and someone needs answer about the product, web site should be able to answer it.
3. **Poor customer service.** Retailers do not want to be rude or disrespectful to their clients. This will make customers disappear quickly. Lack of customer service can be just as bad. He may be nice but not have any answers. How would that look to the customer?
4. **The site is difficult to navigate.** Customers and potential customers should be able to use retailer website easily. It is required to be user friendly. If the site frustrates and confuses then the customer will not stay long and probably not purchase anything.
5. **Not protecting yourself legally.** If there are no terms and conditions for clients to sign or initial electronically then you can get in trouble with lawsuits. Protecting yourself from legalities of a site is important.
6. **Going into business with a partner that is not on the same page.** A difficult partner can destroy the business. They may be thinking one way while you are thinking another. Be sure to work as a team otherwise work alone.
7. **Thinking the product is all you need.** You need customers in order to be successful. Your product can sell but you need someone to buy it. Therefore, be sure to advertise and always have good customer service.
8. **Not understanding marketing.** You will need to be competitive in your prices. Charging too much for a product because you feel as though it is worth that much will not cut it. You have got to be able to know what people are willing to pay for your product. You must also gauge what people can afford. Be effective and economical.
9. **Thinking small.** When you intend for your business to just make enough for you to survive then that will probably be all you will ever make, if that. You need to think big and vision your business as a large company and what you will need to do in order to make it big and keep it big.
10. **Hiring people that are cheap.** Do not hire employees for little pay. This will lead to employees that don't care much about your company and you don't want that. Hire only those that will want to work for you and pay well.
11. **Focusing on one aspect of your business.** You will want to be sure to focus on all areas of your business. Do not give great customer service and lack in tracking what is selling. Keeping stock of everything is also important and needs attention as much as the customer service.

Conclusion

Ultimately the fact is technology may change the outward appearance of the playing field, but the game remains the same. Technology is just a platform for change. How we use the technology to create value for customers is what will determine the future-and that's the opportunity need to be addressed

The goal of this guide is to highlight some of the considerations and concerns of creating an E-Retail business. There is no question that the industry will continue to grow and offer tremendous opportunities to the entrepreneur that is willing to invest the time and effort required to make a business a success. The even better news is that the Internet can be fun and offers the challenge of an ever changing environment.

Retailers will need to research the specific areas that relate directly to their E-Retail business idea and create a business plan for success. Contact the Small Business Development Center for the latest information on business development and advances in e-commerce technology.

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